

CURRENT ISSUES OF DEVELOPING THE KNOWLEDGE OF FUTURE PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS ABOUT SPORT TOURISM

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Abstract: In this article, the theoretical-methodological foundations of the development of the knowledge of the future physical education teachers about tourism, in particular, the current issues, are studied. Also, the tasks of introducing healthy technologies into the educational system, ensuring coherence and continuity, development and socialization goals, and increasing the creativity and creativity of specialists, including physical education teachers, were analyzed.

Key words: physical education, sport, tourism, sports tourism, professional activity, training, component, empirical, pedagogical feature, methodology.

INTRODUCTION. Improving the knowledge, skills, and qualifications of students of higher education institutions worldwide, developing their intellectual and physical maturity, increasing the quality of education, humanizing it, introducing healthy technologies into educational systems, coherence and continuity, development and ensuring socialization goals, increasing the creativity and creativity of specialists, including physical education teachers.

The large-scale reforms implemented in our country make it possible to define the perspective of socio-economic and cultural development and take a worthy place among the countries of the world community. Studying the experiences of the developed countries of the world, taking into account local conditions, economic and intellectual resources, the implementation of fundamental reforms in all spheres of society ensures new achievements. Although international cooperation in various fields is bearing fruit, strengthening national independence in all aspects, enriching the achieved achievements, quickly eliminating existing shortcomings requires special dedication, enthusiasm, courage and requires persistence.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Many studies have been conducted on the development of the professional skills of physical education and sports specialists, and the effective organization of the formation of moral values in athletes. aspects of mental, functional preparation; N.N. Tokhtaboyev, A.N. Shopulatov, S.S. Tajibayev, F. Kerimov, R. Abdumalikov, A. Muzaffarov, A.

Mirzayev, A. Khudoyorov conducted research on improving the training of sports specialists using action games.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. The current development of science, technology, production and technology is determining the shape of modern society. The most important feature of modern society is globalization in all its spheres. Globalization itself requires rapid movement, immediate acquisition of necessary information, their processing and effective implementation. Only personnel who are knowledgeable in their field, have acquired professional skills at a high level, and have rich experience and skills will have the opportunity to move in this way. Therefore, it is appropriate to take into account this demand of the time in the process of training personnel in higher educational institutions.

In our opinion, the upbringing of a physically fit generation and its maturity will be established through the culture of a sustainable lifestyle. The main criterion for it is the individual's health and level of health. Health and well-being go back to the maturity of the human body, and its foundation stone is laid from the earliest period of biological age. Healthy life, active optimal movement activity has its theoretical foundations, but this problem has not been fully studied to date. The analysis of general and special literature and the analytical results of the scientific research conducted in the period after our independence show that it is necessary to conduct fundamental research on the subject. After all, "the aspirations of tourism to take the main place in today's agenda, to increase the educational potential, to increase the share of the tourism sector in reducing poverty, and to strengthen bilateral partnership relations are in harmony with our common goals" [1].

Along with organizing the educational process in our country, he manages it, carries out tasks of state importance, forms the society of the new generation based on state goals [3]. Accordingly, only if the student is ready to organize his activities in a new way, he will organize a psychological process rich in discoveries that have not yet been discovered, and will create the necessary psychological conditions for the formation of a well-rounded personality. Therefore, one of the first steps in improving the quality and efficiency of the educational system is to ensure the readiness of teachers for the professional pedagogical process.

One out of every 10 jobs on the planet is related to travel and tourism. In addition, UNWTO promotes education in the field of tourism and the

development of tourism as an economic sector, among other things, helps to solve the problem of poverty on the planet [2].

According to our point of view, the psychological preparation of the future physical education teacher for professional activity is as follows: to predict the success of the intended innovation and its individual steps; to compare the innovation with other innovations, to select the most effective of them, to determine their most significant and accurate level; checking the level of success of innovation implementation. Training of students for professional activity is carried out in the following steps:

1. Analysis of educational activities in the period before the application of the innovation.
2. Analysis of the period of psychological active formation of professional activity.
3. Analysis of the activity in the period after the innovation was introduced into the editorial process.

As a result of the professional activity of the physical education teacher, the physical readiness of students, individual-psychological characteristics, their motives are thoroughly studied, methodical complexes are created that provide a continuous didactic system for physical training in activities outside the school and auditorium; various competitions, educational events promoting a healthy lifestyle: conversations, parties, sports shows are organized, students' interests in sports are taken into account, they are attracted to sports clubs, students' physical, mental and intellectual abilities are developed; Pedagogical and psychological environment in the family, class and school is thoroughly studied and their cooperation is developed.

In our opinion, the goal of preparing future physical education teachers for professional activity is to form the teacher's desire for innovation, the ability to work independently, using modern pedagogical technologies, interactive methods, and extracurricular activities. Since it is to improve the qualification of conducting classes, the physical education teacher should demonstrate the following skills in professional activity:

- uses creative motivation in classes, evaluates professional activity;
- cooperates in creative interaction of students;
- organizes work with determination, responsibility and honesty;
- determines the need for professional activity;
- prepares to engage in creative activities;
- aligns personal goals with professional activities, etc.

– In addition, in the preparation of the future teacher of physical education for professional activity, it is envisaged to perform the following functions:

– embedding the concepts of national and national values into the content of physical education classes;

– analysis of a conscious approach to future professional activity, a critical approach to standards;

– passion for professional innovations; formation of creativity;

– realizing one's potential, embodying a healthy lifestyle and aspirations in one's professional activity;

– finding new technologies that define effective and relevant standards;

– ensuring a person's development based on self-determination and self-expression;

– establishing effective pedagogical measures for harmoniously conducting education and training, bringing young people to adulthood not only physically, but also spiritually and morally;

– to create a healthy creative environment in educational institutions, to raise the quality of education to a new level by introducing advanced professional, pedagogical and information technologies to the education and training process;

– development of young people's outlook, thinking, independent observation abilities;

– to protect young people from the influence of religious-extremist ideas, various information attacks, to educate in them feelings of patriotism, loyalty to the country and involvement in its fate;

– to fundamentally update the forms and content of extracurricular education, to direct the acquisition of knowledge based on the characteristics of the regions, the interests and wishes of students;

– expanding the scope of innovations in the field of pedagogy, opening a wide path to research on pedagogical diagnostics, individual approach to the personality of the student, introducing a mechanism for their comprehensive support;

– strengthening of the trend of orientation of physical education classes designed to manage student activity in the pedagogical (education, upbringing) process towards a well-rounded personality education.

The development of innovative processes in higher education institutions is carried out based on the unique characteristics of the educational system and legal framework of each country.

According to the theoretical analysis of the literature, it is concluded that the transfer of innovations in the training of future physical education teachers has its own characteristics in Spain. A special model for teaching the secrets of professional activity to future physical education teachers was created, which differs from models in other countries. When discussing the problems of preparing teachers for innovative activities, its assessment, control, monitoring, quality assurance, etc. are taken into account. In the training of physical education teachers in Spain, efficiency and quality are considered the most important indicators in educational institutions. The innovative activity of teachers is evaluated quantitatively based on the overall educational system or its specific stage.

New approaches to the training of future physical education teachers can be conditionally divided into two models.

The model of heuristic approach to the work of future physical education teachers - students studying in the field of physical education and special education of higher educational institutions (HEIs) is used for this. This model was reflected in the book "Physical Culture" by scientist V. I. Lyakh.

The model of creative approach to the work of future physical education teachers is used in Great Britain, USA, Australia, Finland, South Korea, Czechia, and Latvia. In these countries, the innovative activities of physical education teachers will make it possible to identify existing problems and achievements in establishing psychological relations with students, and plan to improve the quality of education.

In France, the activities of physical education teachers are carried out by the National Committee for the Evaluation of Vocational Education and Training. This committee periodically objectively evaluates the state of higher education in the country, reports the results to the parliament and the government, and then to the general public in the form of publications. In Germany and Great Britain, the supervision of the activities of physical education teachers is carried out by special commissions responsible for the educational process.

From the theoretical analysis of the literature, it can be seen that in recent years, an increase in the state budget spent on training physical education teachers for innovative activities has been observed in European countries. In Western Europe, as the programs, knowledge and information received by

students in educational institutions are increasingly transferred outside the institution, the increased international exchange of athletes, students, teachers and researchers, as well as the European labor market indicates that the trend of internationalization of the market has increased. In Germany, the Czech Republic, and Denmark, the activity of physical education teachers is controlled based on the goals, tasks, evaluation criteria of national systems, evaluation criteria of state, public, education departments, and special structures. Although the officially announced goals of evaluation are to maintain or increase quality at the level of established standards, in practice the understanding of this issue itself (from the need for increased control in exchange for the expansion and improvement of reports to the self-determination of quality evaluation by the educational institution) until self-assessment) is observed diversity [5].

Today, the socio-pedagogical need to create a system of motivational approaches and relationships for future physical education teachers is increasing. This makes it an urgent task to improve the system of training and training them as personnel. In this sense, there is a need to train future physical education teachers based on modern students, develop their professional knowledge and skills, and prepare them for innovative activities based on a creative approach.

Due to the fact that the share of physical activities is decreasing in modern conditions, the training of highly qualified specialists in the field of physical education is becoming more and more important as an important issue for all types of education. In a certain sense, modern physical culture education is represented by a problematic situation related to the existing contradictions between the society's objective need for highly qualified physical education specialists and the practical and professional training of graduates.

CONCLUSION. Modern pedagogy involves the use of a motivational approach to develop the professional knowledge and skills of a future physical education teacher, to educate them in a new worldview and thinking, and to use their professional competence at a high level to improve the quality and efficiency of physical education, to create motivational activity and to basically aims to achieve social changes.

One of the urgent tasks is to form the motivation of future physical education teachers to become a skilled master of their profession, to start a professional activity, and to direct their internal motivation for the effectiveness of professional activity.

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